

Finding Optimal BLE Configuration for Indoor Positioning with Consumption Restrictions

2021 Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)

Zenodo package documentation

Abstract

This document contains the description of the supporting material of the work entitled "Finding Optimal BLE Configuration for Indoor Positioning with Consumption Restrictions" and presented in the "2021 Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation conference (IPIN 2021)" published in the Zenodo repository.

1 Introduction

Fingerprinting-based positioning using smartphones has gained significant attention in the indoor positioning research community in recent years. This technique requires minimal additional hardware since it operates with commonly available radio-frequency networks, such as Wi-Fi and Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE), which notably reduces deployment costs.

Wi-Fi has traditionally been the primary technology for fingerprint-based positioning. However, software limitations related to scanning cycles and restricted access to certain data imposed by major smartphone software providers have constrained its suitability for high-precision applications. Despite these limitations, fingerprinting research has continued to thrive, largely due to the advantages offered by BLE, which is not subject to the same restrictions. BLE provides several improvements over Wi-Fi for fingerprinting, including simpler protocols and greater flexibility in transmitter placement. Unlike Wi-Fi access points, which require a power supply and a wired connection, BLE beacons can be placed almost anywhere and powered by batteries for extended periods.

Current research is focused on improving positioning accuracy and leveraging unique features of the BLE protocol, such as utilizing the three advertising channels separately. Most commercially available BLE beacons are designed to be battery-powered, which makes system lifespan highly dependent on battery life. This reliance on batteries can be a challenge for indoor positioning systems with a large number of beacons transmitting continuously, as replacing batteries can be both costly and labor-intensive. Battery duration is primarily influenced by two transmission parameters: transmission power (Tx) and transmission period (Ts). Previous studies have examined how these parameters affect positioning accuracy but have not fully explored their impact on system lifespan. Research indicates that Tx is less critical than transmission frequency for Internet of Things (IoT) applications. Furthermore, the introduction of multi-slot transmitting beacons has added complexity to optimizing configurations for maximum positioning accuracy while maintaining power efficiency over an extended period.

2 Experimental Set-Up and Materials

2.1 Environment

The evaluation area selected for this study was part of a research building at the University of Extremadura, where a BLE infrastructure was installed. This setup facilitated empirical experiments and allowed for the assessment of various configurations for multi-slot BLE-based positioning. The area comprises three distinct zones:

- **Region A** (Fig 2): This region includes a walkway and an inner courtyard.

Figure 1: Pictures of the evaluation area including Region A (a), Region B (b), and Region C (c).

- **Region B** (Fig 2): A larger walkway, approximately 32 m in length, connecting Region A to Region C.
- **Region C** (Fig 2): A corridor approximately 20 m long, lined with offices on both sides.

Figure 2 illustrates the floor plan, showing the three regions, beacon locations, reference points, and test points.

2.2 Beacons and Points Density

Each region was assigned a specific density of reference points (RPs):

- **Region C**: A linear arrangement with one RP per meter, following a straight line down the center of the walkway.
- **Region B**: A grid distribution of RPs with a spacing of 1.5 m between points.
- **Region A**: A similar grid layout as Region B but with 2 m spacing between RPs.

Beacons were placed along the walkway path, with one beacon every 4 m and additional beacons spaced along the courtyard walls. Test points (TPs) were randomly distributed to cover the entire area, with two beacons and one TP positioned outside the system boundaries, as depicted in Figure 2.

2.3 Materials

The experiment utilized iBKS Plus beacons by Accent Systems [1], which are built on the nrf51822 chipset by Nordic Semiconductor [2]. These beacons support up to six simultaneous transmissions across different slots. Each slot's transmission power (Tx) and transmission interval (Ts) can be independently configured using a smartphone application provided by the manufacturer. For this study, 24 beacons were deployed, each powered by four AA batteries. Fresh batteries were installed prior to deployment to avoid potential issues from aged or depleted batteries.

Two smartphones were used to collect RSSI measurements: the Xiaomi Mi 10 Pro and the Xiaomi Mi A3, both equipped with Bluetooth 5.0 and released in 2019. A custom Android application was developed to capture and store the Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI) values.

2.4 Experimental Procedure

The user traversed all reference points (RPs) in sequence as indicated in Figure 2. At each RP, the user paused, holding one phone in each hand and facing the four cardinal directions (north, west, south, and east) for 15 s each. During this period, the application recorded information for each BLE packet detected by the smartphone, including the timestamp, RP identifier, and orientation. The same process was applied to all test points (TPs) but with shorter measurement durations of 5 s, facing a pre-defined direction to simulate a real walking path through the testing area.

Figure 2: Positioning area with Regions A, B, and C, training points (blue squares), test points (red circles), and beacon positions (pink asterisks).

2.5 Beacon Configurations

The experiment was conducted across several beacon configurations. Each transmission slot on the beacons could be set to one of eight predefined Tx levels: 4 dBm, 0 dBm, -4 dBm, -8 dBm, -12 dBm, -16 dBm, -20 dBm, and -30 dBm. Given time constraints, testing all possible combinations ($8^6 = 262,144$) was impractical, so a subset of representative configurations was chosen based on previous studies and experience with multi-slot BLE positioning. The selected configurations included all single-slot combinations and several with three and six activated slots. Table 1 lists the configuration IDs and Tx levels for each of the six slots. For all configurations, the minimum interval between consecutive advertisements from the same slot was set to 100 ms, as supported by the iBKS beacons.

3 Database Description

The database is organized into two main folders, each corresponding to one of the smartphones used during data collection: the Xiaomi Mi 10 and Xiaomi Mi A3. Within each folder, there are subfolders for each configuration or "set" described in Table ???. Files in each set are named according to the format "set_i_ph_j_name.csv", where: "i" represents the set or configuration ID, "j" denotes the smartphone ID, and "name" identifies one of the following data categories:

- **_cdr:** Measurement coordinates associated with each RSS measurement.
- **_code:** Contains six columns where: - Column 1: Set ID, - Column 2: Phone ID, - Column 3: Reference point ID, - Column 4: Orientation ID, - Column 5: Beacon ID, and - Column 6: Slot ID within the specific beacon.

Table 1: Tx values for the tested configurations with Ts 100 ms. Slots 1–4 configured with Eddystone, Slots 5-6 with iBeacon.

Conf. Id	Slot #1	Slot #2	Slot #3	Slot #4	Slot #5	Slot #6
1	4 dBm	–	–	–	–	–
2	0 dBm	–	–	–	–	–
3	–4 dBm	–	–	–	–	–
4	–8 dBm	–	–	–	–	–
5	–12 dBm	–	–	–	–	–
6	–16 dBm	–	–	–	–	–
7	–20 dBm	–	–	–	–	–
8	–30 dBm	–	–	–	–	–
9	4 dBm					
10	–4 dBm					
11	–12 dBm					
12	–20 dBm					
13	4 dBm	4 dBm	4 dBm	–4 dBm	–4 dBm	–4 dBm
14	–4 dBm	–4 dBm	–4 dBm	–12 dBm	–12 dBm	–12 dBm
15	0 dBm	0 dBm	0 dBm	–8 dBm	–8 dBm	–8 dBm
16	4 dBm	4 dBm	–4 dBm	–4 dBm	–12 dBm	–12 dBm
17	0 dBm	0 dBm	–8 dBm	–8 dBm	–16 dBm	–16 dBm
18	–4 dBm	–4 dBm	–12 dBm	–12 dBm	–20 dBm	–20 dBm
19	4 dBm	0 dBm	–4 dBm	–8 dBm	–12 dBm	–16 dBm
20	4 dBm	4 dBm	4 dBm	–	–	–
21	–4 dBm	–4 dBm	–4 dBm	–	–	–
22	–12 dBm	–12 dBm	–12 dBm	–	–	–
23	0 dBm	0 dBm	0 dBm	–	–	–
24	–8 dBm	–8 dBm	–8 dBm	–	–	–
25	–20 dBm	–20 dBm	–20 dBm	–	–	–
26	4 dBm	–4 dBm	–12 dBm	–	–	–
27	0 dBm	–8 dBm	–16 dBm	–	–	–
28	–4 dBm	–12 dBm	–20 dBm	–	–	–

For training, reference points are numbered from 1 to 64 with orientations from 1 to 4 (0° , 90° , 180° , and 270°). In testing, reference point IDs range from 1 to 21, each with one randomly selected orientation that does not match those used during training. Beacon IDs range from 1 to 24, and for each beacon, slot IDs are numbered from 1 to 6.

- **_idxTest:** Boolean vector with test measurement marked as true and training as false.
- **_idxTrain:** Boolean vector with training measurement marked as true and test and false.
- **_rss:** Records Received Signal Strength (RSS) values in dBm.
- **_time:** Unix timestamp in milliseconds, as provided by the Android system, for each packet received.

Attached with the data are three “.csv” files:

- **Beacons_cdr.csv:** Contains the beacon IDs and their respective coordinates.
- **Beacons_Configurations.csv:** Provides the estimated battery lifespan for each beacon, including: (1) the manufacturer’s estimate with alkaline batteries, (2) the manufacturer’s estimate with lithium batteries, and (3) the lifespan estimate calculated using the method proposed in this article.

- **Points_cdr.csv:** Contains the IDs and coordinates for all 64 training points and 21 testing points. This file is used exclusively for environmental plotting, as the database includes the measurement coordinates associated with each RSS value.

4 Provided Software

A MATLAB script called "MAIN.m" is also included in the database. The script loads data for each set, transforms it into matrix format, and computes the position estimations for each test fingerprint using the NN and Wk -NN algorithms. Each set and phone data are loaded into a MATLAB structure with fields corresponding to the contents of each folder described in the previous section.

Below is a brief description of all the MATLAB functions contained in this script:

- **splitTrnTst_fromDataIdx:** Divides a dataset into training and testing sets, preserving the format (MATLAB structure).
- **changeDataToMatrixNotation:** Organizes the raw data structure into a matrix where each row represents a different reference point and orientation, and each column represents a different beacon and slot. Training matrices contain 256 rows (64 points and 4 orientations per point), while testing matrices contain only 21 rows. The number of columns varies depending on the specific configuration.

Outside the MAIN.m script two other functions are provided:

- **wknnAlgorithm:** Implements the Wk -NN algorithm, providing position estimations and computational time. The behaviour of this function is independent of the problem or the meaning of the data, it can be used for different taskt outside fingerprinting positioning.
- **errorAnalysis:** Compares the matrix of real test coordinates with the estimations provided by the previous function to compute the error distribution. The parameters of this distribution are returned as a MATLAB structure.

References

- [1] *iBKS Plus · Accent Systems*, en-US, <https://accent-systems.com/product/ibks-plus/> (accessed on Jul 24, 2020).
- [2] *nRF51822 - Nordic semiconductor*, en, <https://www.nordicsemi.com/en/Products/Low%20power%20short-range%20wireless/nRF51822> (accessed on Jul 24, 2020).